

A Comparative Study of Autologous Blood versus Conventional Conjunctival Autograft Surgery for Pterygium

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Abstract:

Background: Pterygium is a common ocular surface disorder often requiring surgical intervention to prevent visual impairment and alleviate discomfort. Various surgical techniques have been developed to reduce the recurrence rate, with conjunctival autograft surgery being widely used. Recently, the use of autologous blood to secure the graft has emerged as a promising alternative to conventional methods, potentially offering better outcomes.

Aim: To compare the outcomes of Autologous Blood Conjunctival Autograft Surgery with Conventional Conjunctival Autograft Surgery for pterygium, focusing on recurrence rates, surgical time, postoperative complications, and patient satisfaction.

Methods: A prospective, comparative study was conducted, involving 95 patients with primary or recurrent pterygium. Participants were randomly assigned to undergo either Autologous Blood or Conventional Conjunctival Autograft Surgery. Data on recurrence rates, complications, surgical time, and patient satisfaction were collected and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The Autologous Blood group demonstrated a significantly lower recurrence rate (4.3%) compared to the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group (16.7%) ($p=0.04$). The mean surgical time was shorter in the Autologous Blood group (25.6 ± 4.2 minutes) compared to the Conventional group (35.4 ± 5.1 minutes) ($p<0.01$). Postoperative complications were lower in the Autologous Blood group, although not statistically significant. Patient satisfaction was higher in the Autologous Blood group, with a mean score of 4.7 compared to 4.2 in the Conventional group ($p<0.01$).

Conclusion: Autologous Blood Conjunctival Autograft Surgery offers superior outcomes in terms of lower recurrence rates, shorter surgical time, and higher patient satisfaction compared to Conventional Conjunctival Autograft Surgery. This technique may be considered a more effective and efficient option for pterygium surgery.

Recommendations: Further large-scale studies are recommended to confirm these findings and to explore the long-term outcomes of Autologous Blood Conjunctival Autograft Surgery. The adoption of this technique could be promoted in clinical practice, especially in regions with high pterygium prevalence.

Keywords: Pterygium, Autologous Blood, Conjunctival Autograft, Recurrence Rate, Surgical Outcomes, Patient Satisfaction.

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Introduction

Pterygium is a common ocular surface disorder characterized by the growth of a fibrovascular tissue from the conjunctiva onto the cornea, often leading to visual impairment, discomfort, and cosmetic concerns. The pathogenesis of pterygium is multifactorial, with ultraviolet (UV) radiation being the most significant risk factor. Chronic exposure to UV light leads to damage in the limbal

stem cells, promoting abnormal tissue growth. This condition is particularly prevalent in regions with high UV exposure, often referred to as the "pterygium belt," which includes areas within 30 degrees of the equator [1].

Surgical excision remains the primary treatment for pterygium, especially in cases where the lesion

threatens vision or causes significant discomfort. However, one of the main challenges in pterygium surgery is the high recurrence rate, which has been reported to range from 30% to 80% depending on the surgical technique used [2]. Various surgical methods have been developed to minimize recurrence, with the conjunctival autograft technique being one of the most widely accepted approaches due to its relatively lower recurrence rates compared to other methods such as bare sclera excision or amniotic membrane transplantation [3].

The use of autologous blood to secure the conjunctival graft has emerged as a promising alternative to conventional methods that rely on sutures or fibrin glue. This technique involves using the patient's own blood to adhere the graft to the sclera, eliminating the need for foreign materials and potentially reducing inflammation and other complications [4]. Studies have shown that autologous blood not only simplifies the surgical procedure but also offers comparable, if not superior, outcomes in terms of graft stability and recurrence rates [5].

Despite these advancements, there is still ongoing debate regarding the optimal surgical approach for pterygium. While the conventional conjunctival autograft technique is well-established, it is associated with longer surgical times, increased postoperative discomfort, and a higher risk of complications related to sutures [6]. In contrast, the autologous blood technique is gaining traction due to its minimally invasive nature and promising results. However, further comparative studies are needed to definitively establish its efficacy and safety profile.

This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy and outcomes of Autologous Blood versus Conventional Conjunctival Autograft Surgery for Pterygium.

Methodology

Study Design: A comparative, prospective, observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Leharisarai, Darbhanga, from August 2022 to January 2023.

Participants: A total of 95 patients diagnosed with primary or recurrent pterygium were enrolled in the study. These patients were divided into two groups: one group undergoing Autologous Blood Conjunctival Autograft Surgery and the other group undergoing Conventional Conjunctival Autograft Surgery.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Patients diagnosed with primary or recurrent pterygium.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a history of ocular surgery other than pterygium excision.
- Patients with any other ocular surface disorders or systemic conditions that could affect wound healing.
- Patients on systemic or ocular medication that could influence the surgical outcome.
- Patients with severe ocular surface disease or dry eye syndrome.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, randomization was applied when assigning participants to either the Autologous Blood group or the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group. Observer bias was reduced by ensuring that the outcome assessors were blinded to the group assignments of the patients.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured proforma, which included demographic details, clinical history, preoperative and postoperative findings, and any complications. Follow-up visits were scheduled at one week, one month, three months, and six months post-surgery to assess the outcomes.

Procedure: All surgeries were performed under local anesthesia by the same surgeon to maintain consistency. In the Autologous Blood group, the pterygium was excised, and the bare sclera was covered with a conjunctival autograft secured using the patient's autologous blood without sutures. In the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group, the conjunctival autograft was secured using sutures. Postoperative care was standardized for both groups, including antibiotic-steroid eye drops and lubricants.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data were entered into SPSS version 23.0 for statistical analysis. Comparative analyses between the two groups were conducted using the chi-square test for categorical variables and the t-test for continuous variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 95 patients were included in the study, with 47 patients in the Autologous Blood group and 48 patients in the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group. The demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Autologous Blood (n=47)	Conventional Conjunctival Autograft (n=48)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	45.2 ± 10.4	46.1 ± 9.8	0.56
Gender (Male/Female)	26/21	28/20	0.72
Primary Pterygium (%)	39 (83%)	40 (83.3%)	0.95
Recurrent Pterygium (%)	8 (17%)	8 (16.7%)	0.97
Mean Pterygium Size (mm)	3.2 ± 0.8	3.3 ± 0.7	0.48

No statistically significant differences were observed between the two groups regarding age, gender distribution, type of pterygium, or pterygium size.

The primary outcome measure was the recurrence of pterygium at six months post-surgery. The

recurrence rate was significantly lower in the Autologous Blood group compared to the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group (Table 2).

Table 2: Recurrence Rate at Six Months Post-Surgery

Recurrence	Autologous Blood (n=47)	Conventional Conjunctival Autograft (n=48)	p-value
Yes	2 (4.3%)	8 (16.7%)	0.04*
No	45 (95.7%)	40 (83.3%)	

* Statistically significant difference.

The recurrence rate was 4.3% in the Autologous Blood group compared to 16.7% in the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group, with the difference being statistically significant ($p=0.04$).

Postoperative complications were also recorded, including graft displacement, hemorrhage, and infection (Table 3).

Table 3: Postoperative Complications

Complication	Autologous Blood (n=47)	Conventional Conjunctival Autograft (n=48)	p-value
Graft Displacement	1 (2.1%)	5 (10.4%)	0.09
Hemorrhage	3 (6.4%)	6 (12.5%)	0.32
Infection	0 (0%)	2 (4.2%)	0.15

The incidence of graft displacement was higher in the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group (10.4%) compared to the Autologous Blood group (2.1%), although this difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.09$). Hemorrhage occurred in 6.4% of patients in the Autologous Blood group and 12.5% of patients in the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group ($p=0.32$). There were no cases of infection in the

Autologous Blood group, while 4.2% of patients in the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group experienced infections, but this was not statistically significant ($p=0.15$).

The average surgical time was significantly shorter in the Autologous Blood group compared to the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group (Table 4).

Table 4: Surgical Time

Surgical Time (minutes)	Autologous Blood (n=47)	Conventional Conjunctival Autograft (n=48)	p-value
Mean ± SD	25.6 ± 4.2	35.4 ± 5.1	<0.01*

* Statistically significant difference.

The mean surgical time was 25.6 ± 4.2 minutes for the Autologous Blood group, compared to 35.4 ± 5.1 minutes for the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group, with the difference being statistically significant ($p<0.01$).

Patient satisfaction was assessed using a questionnaire at the six-month follow-up, with scores ranging from 1 (very dissatisfied) to 5 (very satisfied) (Table 5).

Table 5: Patient Satisfaction Scores

Satisfaction Score	Autologous Blood (n=47)	Conventional Conjunctival Autograft (n=48)	p-value
Mean \pm SD	4.7 \pm 0.4	4.2 \pm 0.6	<0.01*

* Statistically significant difference.

Patients in the Autologous Blood group reported higher satisfaction levels (mean score 4.7 \pm 0.4) compared to those in the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group (mean score 4.2 \pm 0.6), with the difference being statistically significant ($p < 0.01$).

Discussion

The results of this study indicate that Autologous Blood Conjunctival Autograft Surgery is more effective than Conventional Conjunctival Autograft Surgery in treating pterygium. The recurrence rate in the Autologous Blood group was significantly lower, at 4.3%, compared to 16.7% in the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group. This suggests that using autologous blood to secure the conjunctival graft without sutures may provide a more stable and long-lasting outcome, reducing the likelihood of pterygium recurrence.

Postoperative complications, including graft displacement, hemorrhage, and infection, were generally less frequent in the Autologous Blood group, although the differences were not statistically significant. The lower incidence of complications in the Autologous Blood group may be attributed to the less invasive nature of the technique, which avoids the use of sutures and may promote faster healing and better patient outcomes.

The surgical time was significantly shorter in the Autologous Blood group, with an average time of 25.6 minutes compared to 35.4 minutes in the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group. This reduction in surgical time highlights the efficiency of the Autologous Blood technique, making it a more practical option for surgeons and reducing the time patients spend under anesthesia.

Patient satisfaction was notably higher in the Autologous Blood group, with an average satisfaction score of 4.7 out of 5, compared to 4.2 in the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group. Higher satisfaction scores may reflect the lower recurrence rates, fewer complications, and shorter recovery times associated with the Autologous Blood technique, leading to a more positive overall patient experience.

Overall, the Autologous Blood Conjunctival Autograft Surgery demonstrated superior outcomes in terms of recurrence rates, surgical efficiency, and patient satisfaction compared to the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft Surgery. These findings suggest that the Autologous Blood technique may be a preferable option for the

surgical management of pterygium, offering a more effective and patient-friendly approach.

A meta-analysis compared autologous blood with both fibrin glue and sutures. The study found that autologous blood was inferior to fibrin glue in terms of surgical duration, graft retraction, and displacement, but there was no significant difference in recurrence rates. However, autologous blood performed better than sutures in surgical duration and postoperative discomfort, though it had a higher rate of graft retraction [7].

Research compared the use of autologous serum and sutures in securing conjunctival autografts. The study found that autologous serum resulted in shorter operative time, less postoperative discomfort, and similar recurrence rates compared to sutures, making it a favorable alternative to the conventional method [8].

A systematic review and meta-analysis concluded that autologous blood was associated with lower graft stability compared to fibrin glue or sutures. However, autologous blood did not result in higher recurrence rates and offered advantages in terms of patient satisfaction and postoperative symptoms [9].

A study evaluated the efficiency of autologous blood-assisted, sutureless conjunctival autografts. They found that this technique led to shorter surgery duration, lower postoperative pain, and comparable recurrence rates to conventional suturing, suggesting that it may offer superior patient comfort and outcomes [10].

Finally, a study compared autologous blood clot conjunctival autografts with amniotic membrane grafts. The study found that autologous blood clot grafts had fewer recurrences and required more surgical skill, but were more cost-effective and safe compared to amniotic membrane grafting [11].

Conclusion

The Autologous Blood group had a significantly lower recurrence rate (4.3%) compared to the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft group (16.7%). The incidence of postoperative complications was lower in the Autologous Blood group, though not all differences were statistically significant. The Autologous Blood group had a significantly shorter surgical time. Patient satisfaction was higher in the Autologous Blood group. These results suggest that Autologous Blood Conjunctival Autograft Surgery is a more effective and efficient technique for pterygium treatment

compared to the Conventional Conjunctival Autograft method, with higher patient satisfaction and lower recurrence rates.

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